

PECULIARITIES OF YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN
PARLIAMENTARY ELECTIONS HELD IN 2004 AND 2009

Atakhanov Bakhtiyar

Senior lecturer of "University of Business and Science",

Doctor of Philosophy in History (PhD)

e-mail: ataxanov87@bk.ru

Abstract: In this article, the parliamentary elections held in Uzbekistan and the participation of political parties in it, the environment of party competition, the emphasis on youth in the nomination of candidates by political parties were studied. The article also analyzes the issue of attention to youth in the pre-election programs of political parties.

Key words: political participation, political campaign, election campaign.

Introduction:

Elections held by members of society for the purpose of forming state power are not only a sign or appearance of democracy, but also a necessary condition for its existence. After all, "Every person has the right to participate in the management of his country directly or through freely elected representatives. The will of the people must be the basis of government authority; this will must be expressed on the basis of the secret ballot or other equally important general and equal suffrage that ensures the freedom of voting" is not for nothing stated in Article 21 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The right of citizens to vote, their participation in elections, is a complex of legal norms of procedures that coordinate the relations between voters and elected bodies, as well as recall representatives who have not justified the trust of voters.

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the right to vote for citizens in our country is established from the age of 18, the right to be elected to local representative bodies from the age of 21, to the Oliy Majlis from the age of 25, and to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the age of 35.

Methodology:

Based on the total number of people participating in the elections in our country, it can be said that the majority of voters are young people aged 18 to 30 years. It is certainly interesting for many to find answers to the questions of young people's attitude to the election, their participation, interest, activity in this process, which political party they support the pre-election program.

Literature discussion:

There is one side of the issue, do the aspects we have listed arouse interest among young people? How do young people look at this issue, active or passive? In order to find answers to the above-mentioned questions, a survey was conducted among the students of Namangan State University and the youth of Namangan city. The results of the survey show that 81% of those who participated in the survey know the right to vote and from what age they have this right. "Which state bodies will be elected in Uzbekistan?" 56% of the participants gave a clear answer to the question, but many were hesitant to find the answer to the age at which the right to be elected to state bodies formed on the basis of elections. "On December 21 of this year, the election to which state body will be held?" 49% of the participants gave a clear answer to the question. When we asked some participants to go to the polling station on the election day, some of them gave a sad and funny answer: "I won't go, my father will come and vote instead of everyone in the family."

The second aspect of the issue, that is, the attitude towards the political parties that form the basis of the election and are at the center of it, the majority of the survey participants stated that they have a passive attitude. Even the young people

stated that they have not heard the name of some parties in our country, they have not come across such a name at all. "Do you know the press publications of political parties?" most of the participants did not have a complete and clear answer to the question. According to some participants, it was noted that the live activity of political parties can be observed only during pre-election processes.

The conclusion of the survey shows that young people's attitude towards elections and political parties participating in the elections is not very active. What is the reason for this?

First of all, the issue of raising the political literacy of young people, raising their political consciousness and culture is being considered slowly in educational institutions.

Second, mass media rarely broadcast programs and videos that call young people to social and political activity.

Thirdly, youth organizations in our country are indifferent to the issue of youth political activity in self-governing bodies.

Fourthly, the involvement of youth departments of political parties in our Republic in the society is generally less visible, or the principle of operation of those departments is not clear. Most of the young people in the society do not know that political parties have youth departments and how they work.

In order to increase the political activity of young people, who make up the majority of the population of our country, and to ensure that they do not become indifferent to political processes, political parties should organize their activities more effectively. First of all, political parties should improve the activities of their youth department. It is desirable for parties' youth departments to organize socio-political projects and support initiatives to attract more young people. Although there are various initiatives and projects of youth departments of political parties operating in our country, they are not organized effectively. In particular, the youth wing of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan's "Istiqbol" youth wing

"Young Politician" selection contest is held every year, but the efforts to keep and support young people participating in this event in the party have not been effectively launched. The projects of the Liberal-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan to support young entrepreneurs are not showing effective results either.

In the 2004 and 2009 Oliy Majlis and People's Deputies elections to regional, district and city councils, political parties nominated very few candidates under 30 years of age. In particular, no candidate under the age of 30 was nominated to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis.

Conclusions:

If we approach the above situations from a scientific point of view, the lack of interest of the youth in the political sphere of the society or the insufficient involvement in the political processes is the reason for the emergence of political indifference among the youth in the society. As a result of political indifference, it creates mistrust of the state and authorities of the society. Distrust of the authorities is the reason for sparking the embers of various political conflicts and problems.

If: "Journey to the World of the Constitution", "Fundamentals of State and Law", "Fundamentals of Constitutional Law" lessons at school, "Community and Personality" lessons at colleges and academic lyceums, and "Political Science" and "Newest History of Uzbekistan" subjects in higher education institutions. if they teach and teach young people deeper political knowledge; mass media, in particular, on radio and television, and on the radio, they launch videos, shows and broadcasts that give political knowledge to young people, and socio-political newspapers organize interesting political discussions and columns full of debates, not limited to providing information; If political parties pay more attention to young people when forming their cadres, as well as expand the number of political events and contests that attract young people and expand their opportunities, as well as social networks (Facebook, Twitter, Telegram, etc.) .h.) if the political parties would widely use the opportunity, the political indifference of the youth

would not be allowed in the society. Also, the political parties would have gained wide support of the youth in the elections.

References:

1. [ESTABLISHMENT AND PROSPECTS OF DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND BELARUS.](#) В Ataxonov - Theoretical & Applied Science, 2019
2. [Ўзбекистон ва Беларусь давлатларининг ҳамкорлик алоқалари ва уларнинг ҳуқуқий асослари.](#) Б Атаханов - Взгляд В Прошлое, 2021
3. [Family and Marriage Relations in the Uzbek and Belarusian People in the Middle of the 19th-Early 20th Century.](#) В Atakhanov - International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 2023
4. [Consolidation and development of relations between Uzbekistan and Belarus during the years of independence.](#) A Bakhtiyar - Conferencea, 2022
5. [The significance of official visits in the relations of Uzbekistan and Belarus.](#) AB Turabaevich - Conferencea, 2022
6. [Participation and cooperation of Uzbekistan and Belarus in the Shanghai cooperation organization.](#) A Bakhtiyor - ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary ..., 2022
7. [The role of national and cultural centers in the development of international peace in the country.](#) A Bahtiyor - Asian journal of multidimensional research, 2022
8. [Participation And Cooperation Of Uzbekistan And Belarus In The United Nations.](#) AB Turabaevich - The American journal of interdisciplinary innovations ..., 2021
9. [COOPERATIVE RELATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND BELARUS.](#) AB Turabaevich - Conferencea, 2022

